

MANAGING JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL MATHEMATICS INSTRUCTION

JAMES C. ROYOL

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2846-1020>

jamesroyol80@gmail.com

DepEd Taal National High School, Taal Batangas, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to assess the junior high school mathematics instruction in DepEd Batangas Province to be used as basis in the development of school - based management program. It investigated the profile of the mathematics teachers in terms of their age, sex, highest educational attainment, number of years in teaching mathematics and computer literacy. The school administrators and teachers assessed the management of junior high mathematics instruction using SAMR model the includes substitution, augmentation, modification, and redefinition. It also considered the differences on the responses of two groups along these lines. Further, differences on the responses of mathematics teachers when they are grouped according to their profile variables were also considered. Result of the study was used as basis for the proposed school -based management program. The researcher used the descriptive method of research where questionnaire and interview were employed to collect data from the teachers and school administrators. Frequency/percentage, weighted mean/average, T- test and ANOVA and Scheffe Test were used to statistically treat the data and yielded the following results. Majority belongs to age range of 45-54, female, college graduate and teaches for 1-5 years and proficient in using the computer. They were able to moderately manage the instruction in terms of substitution, augmentation, and modification but only able to slightly manage in terms of redefinition. The two groups of respondents differ on their assessments. Further, there are also significant differences on the assessments of the teachers when they are grouped according to profile variables. Finally, the researcher opted to suggest a program that is believed to address the need to cope and adapt with the demand of the teaching and learning process of junior high school mathematics instruction in the new normal learning environment.

Keywords: Junior High School Mathematics Instruction, Mathematics Instruction, SAMR Model